

Mandibular patterns for termite inquilines (Blattodea: Isoptera)

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Abstract

Mandibles of termite workers present distinct patterns according to the type of material they deal with when foraging and building, being hence useful to distinguish functional groups. This is hardly surprising as, being the tools most frequently and intensely used by workers, mandibles should be constantly subjected to selective forces. If worker mandibles reflect evolutionary pressure one could hence hypothesize that mandible patterns of workers of termite hosts would differ from those of termite inquilines. After all, host and inquilines differ, if nothing, on their differential investment in building activities. Here we test this hypothesis, contrasting the Left Mandible Index (LMI) of host and inquiline termite workers within the Termitidae family, an index known to be connected to foraging and building behaviours. To do so, we run a logistic regression to inspect the effect of LMI on the chance of finding at least one inquiline species among those composing a given genus. We found that there seems to be an upper limit for the LMI above which genera will be more likely to hold at least one inquiline species among its constituents. Such a likelihood attains overwhelming 95% chances for $LMI > 1.86$. Hence, higher LMI values seem to facilitate inquiline behaviour in such termites. We speculate that large LMIs, implying in mandibles with molar plates adapted to soft materials, would not suit building being, hence, more adjusted to inquilines than to hosts. Further studies should reveal whether or not this is adaptive or merely coincidental of termite life modes.

Keywords: symbiosis, inquilinism, left mandible index

1 Introduction

- 1 Morphological traits of organisms are modulated by selective forces arising from
- 2 interactions between factors including environmental circumstances, behavior
- 3

4 and genetic information Wcislo (1989). Examples of it seem readily available
5 among social insects, in which behaviours such as nest construction, foraging,
6 and defense are closely related to differentiation on morphological traits Flores-
7 Prado et al. (2014). The link between morphology and function is most evident
8 in termite soldiers whose wide variety of shape and size of their head structures
9 (mandibles and nasus) correspond neatly to their different defense strategies
10 Scholtz et al. (2008). The same could be thought of termite workers which,
11 being responsible for foraging and feeding the other castes, present mandibular
12 patterns significantly associated to interspecific variation in gut content (Dono-
13 van et al., 2001). In other words, the activities that are more prevalent and
14 relevant to a given caste would contribute more for the selective pressures lead-
15 ing to morphological differentiation. While soldiers would be shaped by defense
16 needs, workers would suffer stronger pressures from foraging as well as nest
17 construction.

18 However, there are termite species that, instead of building their own nest,
19 cohabit in nests built by other termite species. The workers of these so called
20 “inquilines” would not have nest construction as their main task.

21 It follows that selective pressures should differ in nature and intensity for the
22 workers of builder (i.e., host) and non-builder (i.e., inquiline) termite species.
23 Termite workers of host species should be under pressure mostly from construc-
24 tion and foraging while building pressures should not strongly impact inquilines.
25 If indeed worker mandibles reflect evolutionary pressure, as implicit in the semi-
26 nal work of Ahmad (1950), one could hence hypothesize that mandible patterns
27 of workers of termite hosts would differ from those of termite inquilines. Here
28 we test such a hypothesis, contrasting the Left Mandible Index (Emerson, 1960)
29 of host and inquiline termite workers within the Termitidae family. This index
30 describes the development of the apical tooth and is agreed to correlate with the
31 hardness of the materials dealt with by termite workers (Sands, 1965; Mathews,
32 1977a) being hence connected to foraging and building behaviours.

33 2 Materials and Methods

34 We will use the Left Mandible Index (LMI henceforth) as a parameter to con-
35 trast workers of host and inquiline termites. The LMI consist of the distance
36 between left apical and first marginal teeth divided by the distance from first
37 to third marginals. In workers this index is larger the softer the materials they

38 deal with, being in such case accompanied by a strongly concave or cupped
39 molar plate without ridges (Mathews, 1977a, p. 12). On top of its biological
40 significance, this measurement can be easily obtained from actual specimens or
41 from images and drawings of mandibles normally present in the taxonomical
42 literature.

43 Data on LMI was hence compiled from (i) direct measurements of the spec-
44 imens deposited in the Isoptera Section of the Museum of Entomology of the
45 Federal University of Viçosa, Brazil, or those deposited in the Collection of
46 Isoptera of the University of Brasilia, Brazil, and from (ii) measurements taken
47 from drawings of mandibles in published species descriptions. Measurements of
48 specimens were obtained using Leica M205A Stereo Microscope. Measurements
49 taken from the literature were done loading the corresponding PDF image to
50 GIMP 2.8 free & open source image editor (<http://www.gimp.org>). When no
51 PDF was available, a caliper was used onto the printed mandible image. Some
52 data have been extracted directly from Rezende (2012).

53 We focused on all Neotropical Termitidae, in which the second marginal
54 tooth of the left mandible is fused to the first. LMI, thus, is restricted to this
55 family. Since in termites, mandibular patterns are conserved within genera
56 (Ahmad, 1950), our analysis is restricted to this taxonomical level.

57 Data were subjected to logistic regression, a form of generalized linear mod-
58 eling (GLM) under binomial errors, which is suitable for modeling the effects
59 of one or more continuous or categorical explanatory variables on a binary re-
60 sponse variable Logan (2010). We aimed to determine the effects of the continu-
61 ous explanatory variable “Left Mandible Index” (x-var) on the binary response
62 variable “presence/absence of inquiline species in the genus” (y-var). A single
63 record of an inquiline species belonging to a given genus would confer the sta-
64 tus of “present” to its y-var. Conversely, genera whose composing species have
65 never been recorded as inquilines would be represented by an y-var with the
66 status of “absent”. Present and absent status are coded, respectively, as 1 and
67 0. Our logistic model, therefore, models the likelihood that a given genus bear-
68 ing a given LMI value would hold at least one inquiline among its composing
69 species.

70 We used a GLM to test whether a sigmoid curve with an asymptote towards 0
71 and 1 at the y-axis (i.e., a logistic model) fitted the data better than a horizontal
72 line parallel to the x-axis intercepting the y-axis at 0.5 (i.e., equal chances
73 of presence or absence). The choice of this sigmoid function (H_1) over the
74 horizontal line (H_0) would establish a relationship between LMI and inquilinism

75 and also show that there is a critical LMI above which termites species are
76 more likely to be inquilines (i.e., likelihood >50 %). This critical size would
77 correspond to the inflection point of the sigmoid curve.

78 Analyses were performed in R (R Core Team, 2015), followed by residual
79 analysis to check the suitability of the error distribution and model fitting.

80 **3 Results**

81 LMI varied from 0.24 to 2.79 among all 79 Neotropical Termitidae genera (Ta-
82 ble 1). Genera holding at least one inquiline among their component species
83 presented highly variable LMI, ranging from 0.29 to 2.79, such extreme val-
84 ues corresponding to *Velocitermes* and *Genuotermes* respectively. Exclusive
85 host genera, that is, those holding no inquiline species among their component
86 species, presented a more restricted range of LMI, varying only from 0.24 (*Con-*
87 *strictotermes*) to 1.31 (*Anhangatermes*).

88 The likelihood of holding at least a inquiline among its composing species is
89 related to the genus LMI according to the logistic equation:

$$\log(p/q) = -0.8503 + 2.041 * LMI$$

90 where (p/q) is the odds ratio of the chance p of success (the chance of being an
91 inquiline) and the chance q of insuccess (the chance of being not an inquiline)
92 in finding an inquiline species and LMI is the Left Mandible Index. From
93 the equation above, the turning point where the chance of being an inquiline
94 becomes larger than 50% ($p = 0.50$, $q = 0.50$) is $LMI = 0.42$ whereas this
95 chance is larger than 95% ($p = 0.95$, $q = 0.05$) from $LMI = 1.86$.

96 In other words, LMI can be said to significantly affect the probability of
97 being an inquiline ($P = 0.0000007$); the larger the LMI of a genus, the higher
98 the probability of finding at least one inquiline among its species (Figure 1).
99 A Neotropical Termitidae genus whose left mandible index is higher than 1.86
100 will have a chance larger than 95% to have an inquiline among its constituent
101 species.

102 **4 Discussion**

103 Our results support the hypothesis that workers of host and inquiline termites
104 differ in their mandibular patterns, at least in the Neotropical Termitidae. There

105 seems to be an upper limit for the Left Mandible Index (LMI) above which gen-
106 era will be more like to hold at least one inquiline species among its components.
107 Such a likelihood attains overwhelming 95% chances for $LMI > 1.86$. Moreover,
108 genera holding inquiline species seem to present much higher variation in LMI
109 than genera in which the constituent species are exclusive hosts. Stated in an-
110 other way, higher LMI values seem to facilitate inquilinistic behaviour in such
111 termites while, nevertheless, lower values do not prevent it.

112 A clearer view of these results seems to arise perusing Table 1: typical in-
113 quilines such as *Inquilinitermes* or *Spinitermes* present LMI values > 2 while
114 LMI values < 1 are characteristic of genera such as *Velocitermes* and *Embirater-*
115 *mes* which are equally found as inquilines or living in their own nests.

116 The reasons for such a pattern are still speculative and we present them here
117 only as a guideline for further studies. It is tempting, for instance, to associate
118 the above mandibular patterns to the main tasks performed by workers, spe-
119 cially considering the conections between LMI and soft diet. Large LMIs, being
120 associated with strongly concave molar plates void of ridges (Mathews, 1977a),
121 are indicative of a humus-feeding (as opposed to wood-feeding) diet (Sands,
122 1965) being hence associated to the handling of softer materials. This is in line
123 with recent studies showing highly humified material to be the main diet of a
124 wide range of inquiline species (Florencio et al., 2013).

125 An alternative (yet hypothetical) line of thought would remind us that a
126 large LMI reflects a disproportionately large, often falciform, apical tooth. It
127 does seem plausible to suspect this tooth to be used as a weapon to defend
128 inquiline workers from their hosts. Mandibles with large LMIs seem, again,
129 highly suitable to inquiline workers.

130 Such a strong specialization could compromise, on the other hand, the suit-
131 ability of these mandibles for tasks such as building. When engaged in building,
132 termite workers use their mandibles as tools to chew and mix construction ma-
133 terials (basically soil particles) with saliva and then to deposit those masses on
134 some organized way to form the nest structures (Emerson, 1938). Facilform
135 mandibles with molar plates adapted to soft materials would not seem suitable
136 for such a job being, hence, more adjusted to inquilines than to hosts. After all,
137 building demands are *per definition* stronger upon hosts than on inquilines.

138 Clearly, albeit still needing further testing, these hypotheses seem to derive
139 straightly from the new pattern here established: large LMI values in worker
140 mandibles are strongly related to inquilinistic habits in Neotropical Termitidae.
141 Whether or not this is adaptive or merely coincidental of this mode of life should

142 be revealed by deeper investigation.

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152 References

- 153 Acioli, A.N.S. et al. (2007). Revisão taxonômica e relações filogenéticas do
154 gênero Neotropical *Ruptitermes* Mathews, 1977 (Isoptera: Termitidae: Api-
155 cotermitinae).
- 156 Ahmad, M. (1950). The phylogeny of termite genera based on imago-worker
157 mandibles. Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History, 95: 41–95.
- 158 Bourguignon, T., Scheffrahn, R.H., Křeček, J., Nagy, Z.T., Sonet, G. & Roisin,
159 Y. (2010). Towards a revision of the Neotropical soldierless termites (Isoptera:
160 Termitidae): redescription of the genus *Anoplotermes* and description of
161 *Longustitermes*, gen. nov. Invertebrate Systematics, 24: 357–370.
- 162 Bourguignon, T., Scheffrahn, R.H., Nagy, Z.T., Sonet, G., Host, B. & Roisin, Y.
163 (2016). Towards a revision of the Neotropical soldierless termites (Isoptera:
164 Termitidae): redescription of the genus *Grigiotermes* Mathews and descrip-
165 tion of five new genera. Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society, 176: 15–35.
- 166 Canello, E.M. & Noirot, C. (2003). *Paraconvexitermes acangapua* (Isoptera:
167 Termitidae, Nasutitermitinae), a new genus and new species of the so-called
168 “small Neotropical soil-feeding nasutes” from south america. In Annales de
169 la Société entomologique de France, vol. 39, (pp. 187–193). Taylor & Francis.
- 170 Carrijo, T.F. & Canello, E.M. (2011). *Divinotermes* (Isoptera, Termitidae,
171 Termitinae), a new genus from south america. Sociobiology, 58: 537–556.
- 172 Carrijo, T.F., Cuezco, C. & Santos, R.G. (2015a). *Tiunatermes mariuzani* gen.
173 nov. et sp. nov., a new nasute termite from the Brazilian Savannah (Isoptera:
174 Termitidae). Austral Entomology, 54: 358–365.
- 175 Carrijo, T.F., Rocha, M.M., Cuezco, C., Canello, E.M. et al. (2011). Key to
176 the soldiers of *Angularitermes* Emerson with a new species from Brazilian
177 Amazonia (Isoptera: Termitidae: Nasutitermitinae). Zootaxa, 2967: 61–68.

- 178 Carrijo, T.F., Scheffrahn, R.H. & KŘEČEK, J. (2015b). *Compositermes bani* sp.
179 n. (Isoptera, Termitidae, Apicotermitinae), a new species of soldierless termite
180 from Bolivia. *Zootaxa*, 3941: 294–298.
- 181 Carvalho, S.H. & Constantino, R. (2011). Taxonomic revision of the Neotropical
182 termite genus *Curvitermes* Holmgren (Isoptera: Termitidae: Syntermitinae).
183 *Sociobiology*, 57: 643.
- 184 Constantino, R. (1990). *Anhangatermes macarthuri*, a new genus and species
185 of soil-feeding nasute termite from Amapá, Brazil (Isoptera, Termitidae, Na-
186 sutitermitinae). *Goeldiana Zoologia*, 3: 1–6.
- 187 Constantino, R. (1991a). Notes on *Neocapritermes* Holmgren, with description
188 of two new species from the Amazon Basin (Isoptera, Termitidae, Termiti-
189 nae). Departamento de Zoologie do Museu Paraense Emílio Goeldi.
- 190 Constantino, R. (1991b). *Ereymatermes rotundiceps*, new genus and species
191 of termite from the Amazon Basin (Isoptera, Termitidae, Nasutitermitinae).
192 *Goeldiana Zoologia*, 8: 1–11.
- 193 Constantino, R. (1994). A new genus of *Nasutitermitinae* with mandibulate
194 soldiers from tropical North America (Isoptera: Termitidae). *Sociobiology*,
195 25: 285–294.
- 196 Constantino, R. (1995). Revision of the neotropical termite genus *Syntermes*
197 Holmgren (Isoptera: Termitidae). Ph.D. thesis, University of Kansas.
- 198 Constantino, R. (1998). Description of a new *Planicapritermes* from Cen-
199 tral Amazonia, with Notes on the Morphology of the Digestive Tube of the
200 Neocapritermes-Planicapritermes Group. *Sociobiology*, 32: 109–118.
- 201 Constantino, R. (1999). Chave ilustrada para identificação dos gêneros de cupins
202 (Insecta: Isoptera) que ocorrem no Brasil. *Papéis avulsos de Zoologia*, 40:
203 387–448.
- 204 Constantino, R. (2002). Notes on the type-species and synonymy of the genus
205 *Nasutitermes* (Isoptera: Termitidae: Nasutitermitinae). *Sociobiology*, 40:
206 533–538.
- 207 Constantino, R. (2012). Description of the imago of *Noirotitermes noiroti*
208 Cancellato and Myles 2000 (Isoptera: Termitidae: Syntermitinae), with new
209 records. *Zootaxa*, 3174: 65–68.
- 210 Constantino, R. & Acioli, A.N. (2009). *Ngauratermes arue*, new genus and
211 species of nasute termite (Isoptera: Termitidae) from the Amazon. *Zootaxa*,
212 2239: 22–30.
- 213 Constantino, R., Acioli, A.N., Schmidt, K., Cuezso, C., Carvalho, S.H. & Vas-
214 concellos, A. (2006). A taxonomic revision of the Neotropical termite genera
215 *Labiotermes* Holmgren and *Paracornitermes* Emerson (Isoptera: Termitidae:
216 Nasutitermitinae). *Zootaxa*, 1340: 1–44.

- 217 Constantino, R. & Carvalho, S.H. (2012). A taxonomic revision of the Neotrop-
218 ical termite genus *Cyrrillitermes* Fontes (Isoptera, Termitidae, Syntermiti-
219 nae). *Zootaxa*, 3186: 25–41.
- 220 Costa-Leonardo, A.M. & Barsotti, R.C. (1996). Soldier head morphology of the
221 Neotropical termites: *Embiratermes festivellus* Silvestri and *Spinitermes bre-*
222 *vicornutus* (Desneux)(Isoptera, Termitidae). *Revista Brasileira de Zoologia*,
223 13: 321–330.
- 224 Cuezco, C., Canello, E.M. & Carrijo, T.F. (2017). *Sandsitermes* gen. nov., a
225 new nasute termite genus from South America (Isoptera, Termitidae, Nasu-
226 titermitinae). *Zootaxa*, 4221: 562–574.
- 227 Cuezco, C., Canello, E.M. et al. (2009). A new species of *Obtusitermes*
228 (Isoptera, Termitidae, Nasutitermitinae) from South America. *Zootaxa*, 1993:
229 61–68.
- 230 Cuezco, C. & Nickle, D.A. (2011). A new genus and species of termites (Isoptera,
231 Termitidae, Nasutitermitinae) from the rainforest of northern Peru. *ZooKeys*,
232 (p. 1).
- 233 Donovan, S.E., Eggleton, P. & Bignell, D.E. (2001). Gut content analysis and a
234 new feeding group classification of termites. *Ecological Entomology*, 26: 356–
235 366. doi:10.1046/j.1365-2311.2001.00342.x. URL [http://doi.wiley.com/](http://doi.wiley.com/10.1046/j.1365-2311.2001.00342.x)
236 [10.1046/j.1365-2311.2001.00342.x](http://doi.wiley.com/10.1046/j.1365-2311.2001.00342.x).
- 237 Emerson, A.E. (1938). Termite nests—a study of the phylogeny of behavior.
238 *Ecological Monographs*, (pp. 247–284).
- 239 Emerson, A.E. (1950). Five new genera of termites from South America
240 and Madagascar (Isoptera, Rhinotermitidae, Termitidae). *American Museum*
241 *novitates*; no. 1444.
- 242 Emerson, A.E. (1952). The neotropical genera *Procornitermes* and *Cornitermes*
243 (Isoptera, Termitidae). *Bulletin of the amnh*; v. 99, article 8.
- 244 Emerson, A.E. (1960). New genera of termites related to *Subulitermes* from the
245 Oriental, Malagasy, and Australian regions (Isoptera, Termitidae, Nasutiter-
246 mitinae). *American Museum novitates*; no. 1986.
- 247 Florencio, D., Marins, A., Rosa, C., Cristaldo, P., Araújo, A., Silva, I. & DeS-
248 ouza, O. (2013). Diet segregation between cohabiting builder and inquiline
249 termite species. *PLoS ONE*, 8: e66535.
- 250 Flores-Prado, L., Pinto, C.F., Rojas, A. & Fontúrbel, F.E. (2014). Strong
251 selection on mandible and nest features in a carpenter bee that nests in two
252 sympatric host plants. *Ecology and evolution*, 4: 1820–1827.
- 253 Fontes, L.R. (1986). Morphology of the alate and worker mandibles of the soil-
254 feeding nasute termites (Isoptera, Termitidae, Nasutitermitinae) from the
255 Neotropical region. *Revista brasileira de Zoologia*, 3: 503–531.

- 256 Holmgren, N. (1912). Termitenstudien. 3. Systematik der Termiten. Die Fami-
257 lien Metatermitidae. K. Svenska Vetensk. Akad. Handl., 48: 1–166.
- 258 Krishna, K. (1968). Phylogeny and generic reclassification of the Capritermes
259 complex (Isoptera, Termitidae, Termitinae). Bulletin of the amnh; v. 138,
260 article 5.
- 261 Krishna, K. (2003). A new species, *Cavitermes rozeni* (Isoptera: Termitidae:
262 Termitinae), from Brazil. Journal of the Kansas Entomological Society, (pp.
263 92–95).
- 264 Light, S. (1933). Termites of Western Mexico, by S.F. Light. University of
265 California. URL <https://books.google.com.br/books?id=q-PhAQAAAJ>.
- 266 Logan, M. (2010). Biostatistical Design and Analysis Using R. 546 pp., Wiley-
267 Blackwell Publishing.
- 268 Mathews, A. (1977a). Studies on termites from the Mato Grosso state, Brazil.
269 Rio de Janeiro: Academia Brasileira de Ciências.
- 270 Mathews, A.A. (1977b). Studies on termites from the Mato Grosso state, Brazil.
271 Academia brasileira de ciências Rio de Janeiro.
- 272 Miller, L. (1984). The Australian genera of the *Subulitermes* branch of the
273 Nasutitermitinae (Isoptera: Termitidae). Austral Entomology, 23: 119–125.
- 274 Oliveira, D.E., Rocha, M.R. & Canello, E.M. (2014). *Muelleritermes*: A new
275 termite genus with two species from the Brazilian Atlantic Forest (Isoptera:
276 Termitidae: Nasutitermitinae). Zootaxa, 4012: 258–270.
- 277 R Core Team (2015). R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Com-
278 puting. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. URL
279 <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- 280 Rezende, P.B. (2012). Hábitos alimentares de cupins sul-americanos da família
281 Termitidae (Insecta: Isoptera).
- 282 ROCHA, M., CANCELLO, E. & Carrijo, T.F. (2012). Neotropical termites:
283 revision of *Armitermes* Wasmann (Isoptera, Termitidae, Syntermitinae) and
284 phylogeny of the *Syntermitinae*. Systematic Entomology, 37: 793–827.
- 285 Rocha, M., Canello, E.M. et al. (2009). Revision of the Neotropical ter-
286 mite genus *Orthognathotermes* Holmgren (Isoptera: Termitidae: Termitinae).
287 Zootaxa, 2280: 1–26.
- 288 Rocha, M.M. (2013). Redescription of the enigmatic genus *Genuotermes* Emer-
289 son (Isoptera, Termitidae, Termitinae). ZooKeys, (p. 107).
- 290 Rocha, M.M., Canello, E.M. & Cuezso, C. (2011). A new genus and species
291 of mandibulate nasute termite (Isoptera, Termitidae, Syntermitinae) from
292 Brazil. ZooKeys, (p. 125).

- 293 Rocha, M.M., Carrijo, T.F., Canello, E.M. et al. (2012). An illustrated key
294 to the soldiers of *Cyranotermes* Araujo with a new species from Amazonia
295 (Isoptera: Termitidae: Nasutitermitinae). *Zootaxa*, (pp. 50–57).
- 296 Rocha, M.M.d. & Canello, E.M. (2007). Estudo taxonômico de *Cylindrotermes*
297 Holmgren (Isoptera, Termitidae, Termitinae). *Papéis Avulsos de Zoologia*
298 (São Paulo), 47: 137–152.
- 299 Roisin, Y., Scheffrahn, R.H. & Křeček, J. (1996). Generic revision of the smaller
300 nasute termites of the Greater Antilles (Isoptera, Termitidae, Nasutitermiti-
301 nae). *Annals of the Entomological Society of America*, 89: 775–787.
- 302 Roonwal, M.L. & Chhotani, O.B. (1966). Revision of termite genus *EURY-*
303 *TERMES* (Termitidae: Amitermitinae). *Proc. natnl. Inst. Sci. India (B)*, 31:
304 31–81.
- 305 Sands, W.A. (1965). A revision of the termite sub-family *Nasutitermitinae*,
306 (Isoptera, Termitidae) from the Ethiopian region. *Bulletin of the British*
307 *Museum (Natural History), Entomology*, 4: 1–172.
- 308 Scheffrahn, R.H. & Křeček, J. (1993). *Parvitermes subtilis*, a new subter-
309 ranean termite (Isoptera: Termitidae) from Cuba and the Dominican Re-
310 public. *Florida Entomologist*, (pp. 603–607).
- 311 Scheffrahn, R.H., Su, N.Y., Chase, J.A. & Forschler, B.T. (2001). New termite
312 (Isoptera: Kalotermitidae, Rhinotermitidae) records from Georgia. *Journal*
313 *of Entomological Science*, 36: 109–113.
- 314 Scheffrahn, R.H. et al. (2010). An extraordinary new termite (Isoptera: Ter-
315 mitidae: Syntermitinae: Rhynchotermes) from the pasturelands of northern
316 Colombia. *Zootaxa*, 2387: 63–68.
- 317 Scholtz, O.I., Macleod, N. & Eggleton, P. (2008). Termite soldier defence
318 strategies: a reassessment of Prestwich’s classification and an examination
319 of the evolution of defence morphology using extended eigenshape analyses of
320 head morphology. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 153: 631–650.
321 doi:10.1111/j.1096-3642.2008.00396.x. URL [http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/
322 j.1096-3642.2008.00396.x](http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.1096-3642.2008.00396.x).
- 323 Snyder, T.E. (1926). Five new termites from Panama and Costa Rica. Cinco
324 nuevas termitas de Panamá y Costa Rica. *Proceedings of the Entomological*
325 *Society of Washington.*, 28: 7–21.
- 326 Wasmann, E. (1897). *Termiten von Madagaskar und Ostafrika*, vol. 1. Diester-
327 weg.
- 328 Wcislo, W.T. (1989). Behavioral environments and evolutionary change. *Annual*
329 *Review of Ecology and Systematics*, 20: 137–169.

Table 1: Left Mandible Index (LMI) of termite (Blattodea: Isoptera) workers belonging to all Neotropical Termitidae genera, classified according to the existence of at least one species recorded as inquiline of another termite species (Inq=1) or the absence of such a record (Inq=0). See M&M for details on how LMI was obtained.

Genus	LMI	LMI source	Inq	Recorded as inquiline by
Acangaobitermes	1.06	Rocha et al. (2011)	1	
Agnathotermes	1.70	Rezende (2012)	1	Constantino (1990)
Amitermes	0.6	Scheffrahn et al. (2001)	0	
Amplucrutermes	0.41	Bourguignon et al. (2016)	0	
Angularitermes	1.01	Rezende (2012)	1	Carrijo et al. (2011)
Anhangatermes	1.31	Constantino (1990)	0	
Anoplotermes	0.35	Bourguignon et al. (2010)	1	Bourguignon et al. (2010)
Antillitermes	0.41	Roisin et al. (1996)	1	Roisin et al. (1996)
Aparatermes	0.48	Constantino (1999)	0	
Araujotermes	0.48	Rezende (2012)	1	Constantino (1991b)
Armitermes	0.90	Rezende (2012)	1	ROCHA et al. (2012)
Atlantitermes	0.84	Rezende (2012)	1	Fontes (1986)
Caetetermes	0.49	Constantino (1999)	1	Constantino (1999)
Cahuallitermes	0.5	Constantino (1994)	0	
Caribitermes	0.38	Roisin et al. (1996)	0	
Cavitermes	0.7	Krishna (2003)	1	Krishna (2003)
Coatitermes	1.27	Rezende (2012)	0	
Coendutermes	0.47	Constantino (1999)	1	Constantino (1999)
Compositermes	0.56	Carrijo et al. (2015b)	1	Carrijo et al. (2015b)
Constrictotermes	0.24	Rezende (2012)	0	
Convexitermes	0.65	Rezende (2012)	1	Fontes (1986)
Cornicapritermes	0.32	Emerson (1950)	0	
Cornitermes	1.37	Emerson (1952)	1	Emerson (1952)
Cortaritermes	0.47	Rezende (2012)	0	
Crepititermes	2.09	Rezende (2012)	1	Mathews (1977b)
Curvitermes	2.17	Rezende (2012)	1	Carvalho & Constantino (2011)
Cylindrotermes	0.33	Rezende (2012)	0	
Cyranotermes	2.24	Rezende (2012)	1	Rocha et al. (2012)
Cyrilliotermes	2.1	Constantino & Carvalho (2012)	1	Constantino & Carvalho (2012)
Dentispicotermes	1.29	Rezende (2012)	1	Constantino (1999)
Dihoplotermes	0.94	Rezende (2012)	1	Krishna (1968)
Diversitermes	0.38	Rezende (2012)	1	Snyder (1926)
Divinotermes	0.7	Carrijo & Canello (2011)	1	Carrijo & Canello (2011)
Embirationtermes	0.86	Constantino (1999)	1	Constantino (1999)
Ereymatermes	1.43	Rezende (2012)	1	Constantino (1991b)
Genuotermes	2.79	Rezende (2012)	1	Rocha (2013)

to be continued...

Table 1: (continued...)

Genus	LMI	LMI source	Inq	Recorded as inquiline by
Grigioterme	0.47	Mathews (1977b)	1	Mathews (1977b)
Hoplotermes	0.70	Roonwal & Chhotani (1966)	0	
Humuterme	0.26	Bourguignon et al. (2016)	0	
Hydrecotermes	0.40	Bourguignon et al. (2016)	0	
Ibiterme	1.17	Rezende (2012)	0	
Inquiliniterme	2.67	Rezende (2012)	1	Mathews (1977b)
Labioterme	1.4	Rezende (2012)	1	Constantino et al. (2006)
Longustiterme	0.63	Bourguignon et al. (2010)	0	
Macuxiterme	0.52	Constantino (1999)	0	
Mapinguariterme	0.77	Rezende (2012)	0	
Microcerotermes	0.57	Rezende (2012)	0	
Muelleriterme	0.52	Oliveira et al. (2014)	0	
Nasutiterme	0.35	Rezende (2012)	0	
Neocapriterme	0.45	Rezende (2012)	1	Constantino (1991a)
Ngauraterme	0.48	Rezende (2012)	1	Constantino & Acioli (2009)
Noirotiterme	1.22	Rezende (2012)	1	Constantino (2012)
Obtusiterme	0.46	Rezende (2012)	1	Cuezzo et al. (2009)
Onkotermes	0.43	Constantino (2002)	0	
Orthognathotermes	1.44	Rezende (2012)	1	Rocha et al. (2009)
Paraconvexiterme	1.22	Rezende (2012)	1	Cancello & Noirot (2003)
Paracurviterme	2.66	Rocha & Cancello (2007)	1	Rocha & Cancello (2007)
Parviterme	0.39	Rezende (2012)	1	Scheffrahn & Křeček (1993)
Patawaterme	0.40	Bourguignon et al. (2016)	1	Bourguignon et al. (2016)
Planicapriterme	0.43	Rezende (2012)	0	
Procorniterme	0.35	Emerson (1952)	1	Emerson (1952)
Rychotermes	0.37	Scheffrahn et al. (2010)	1	Scheffrahn et al. (2010)
Rotunditerme	0.49	Rezende (2012)	0	
Rounditerme	0.43	Constantino (1998)	0	
Rubeotermes	0.46	Bourguignon et al. (2016)	0	
Ruptiterme	0.33	Rezende (2012)	1	Mathews (1977b)
Sandsiterme	0.47	Cuezzo et al. (2017)	0	
Silvestriterme	0.66	Rocha et al. (2012)	1	Rocha et al. (2012)
Sinqasapaterme	0.81	Cuezzo & Nickle (2011)	0	
Spiniterme	2.45	Rezende (2012)	1	Costa-Leonardo & Barsotti (1996)
Subuliterme	0.93	Rezende (2012)	1	Miller (1984)
Syntermes	1.75	Constantino (1995)	1	Constantino (1995)
Tenuirostriterme	0.29	Light (1933)	0	
Termes	1.23	Rezende (2012)	1	Wasmann (1897)
Tetimaterme	0.40	Acioli et al. (2007)	1	Acioli et al. (2007)
Tiunaterme	1.54	Carrijo et al. (2015a)	1	Carrijo et al. (2015a)
Triangulariterme	0.51	Rezende (2012)	1	Mathews (1977b)

to be continued...

Table 1: (continued...)

Genus	LMI	LMI source	Inq	Recorded as inquiline by
Uncitermes	0.50	Rocha et al. (2012)	0	
Velocitermes	0.29	Rezende (2012)	1	Holmgren (1912)

Figure 1: The effects of the workers' left mandible index (LMI) on the probability of finding at least one inquiline species among components of a given termite genera (Blattodea: Isoptera). Each dot is a Neotropical termite genus listed in Table 1. Critical transitional points are signed by dotted lines representing the LMI values above which the probability of finding an inquiline species in that genus exceeds 50% and 95%.